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Data management plan (DMP)

Home Advantage in Professional Football – Research Data Management Project

Home Advantage in Football

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	22/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project
1.1	23/11/2025	Updated data sources section to include detailed information about reused datasets (R1, R2)
1.2	25/11/2025	Added produced datasets table and refined documentation
1.3	25/11/2025	Added ORCID number

1.4	30/11/2025	Updated storage and backup, data publication and long-term preservation tables, data quality control, and licensing/rights of use to reflect TU Wien Research Data and Zenodo deposits
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Level of distribution		<p>This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).</p> <p>This DMP is not published in a public repository and does not have a DOI.</p>
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FWF Data Management Plan (DMP)

I General Information																																		
I.1 Administrative information	<p>PI: Bartosz Ciesielski, bartosz.ciesielski@student.tuwien.ac.at, ORCID: 0009-0003-9034-3102, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62, Project Leader</p> <p>FWF project number:</p> <p>Internal Project ID:</p> <p>DMP version: 01, 22.11.2025</p> <p>Contributors:</p> <p>Tomasz Miksa, tomasz.miksa@tuwien.ac.at, ORCID: 0000-0002-4929-7875, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62, Hosting Institution</p>																																	
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Person responsible for data management and DMP: Bartosz Ciesielski, bartosz.ciesielski@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62</p> <p>Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners: Bartosz Ciesielski, bartosz.ciesielski@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62</p> <p>Resources costed in for RDM: There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.</p>																																	
II Data Characteristics																																		
II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data	<p>Produced datasets:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr style="color: #4F81BD;"> <th>dataset ID</th> <th>title</th> <th>type</th> <th>format</th> <th>estimated volume</th> <th>contains sensitive data</th> <th>description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>P1</td> <td>all_matches</td> <td>Tabular data</td> <td>CSV/XLSX</td> <td>~50–100 KB</td> <td>no</td> <td>Full combined match dataset with basic preprocessing applied</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P2</td> <td>league_results_counts</td> <td>Tabular data</td> <td>CSV/XLSX</td> <td>~50–100 KB</td> <td>no</td> <td>Match result counts grouped by league</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P3</td> <td>league_results_percent</td> <td>Tabular data</td> <td>CSV/XLSX</td> <td>~50–100 KB</td> <td>no</td> <td>Match result percentages grouped by league</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data	description	P1	all_matches	Tabular data	CSV/XLSX	~50–100 KB	no	Full combined match dataset with basic preprocessing applied	P2	league_results_counts	Tabular data	CSV/XLSX	~50–100 KB	no	Match result counts grouped by league	P3	league_results_percent	Tabular data	CSV/XLSX	~50–100 KB	no	Match result percentages grouped by league
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P4	overall_distribution	Tabular data	CSV/XLSX	~50–100 KB	no	Overall distribution of match outcomes across both leagues
P5	summary_all_matches	Tabular data	CSV/XLSX	~50–100 KB	no	Summary statistics for all matches combined
P6	summary_by_league	Tabular data	CSV/XLSX	~50–100 KB	no	Summary statistics grouped by league

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data	description
R1	Professional football match results (Ekstraklasa)	https://www.football-data.co.uk/poland.php	Publicly available historical match and odds data, free to download for personal and research use; further reuse must comply with the general terms and conditions of football-data.co.uk. No explicit open licence is stated; attribution to the source will be provided in all outputs	no	Historical match results for the Polish Ekstraklasa downloaded as CSV files from football-data.co.uk. The dataset contains one row per match with date, home and away team, full-time goals, match outcome (home win/draw/away win) and associated betting odds. No personal or sensitive data are included.
R2	Professional football match results	https://github.com/jalapic/engsoccerdata/tree/master/data	Openly available via the "engsoccerdata" GitHub repository. The data are released under the GPL (≥	no	Historical match results for the English Premier League obtained

	(Premier League)		2) license and described as free to use for non-commercial purposes; reuse requires attribution to the engsoccerdata project and the original author		from the "engsoccerdata" repository. The dataset provides season-by-season league results with one row per match, including date, home and away team, goals scored, match outcome and league/season identifiers. No personal or sensitive data are included.
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Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Existing football match datasets (R1 and R2) are reused and processed using Python (pandas) and Jupyter Notebooks. Raw CSV files are stored in /data/raw/, while all derived tabular outputs (P1–P6) are written to /data/processed/. These processing steps generate new, aggregated datasets but do not introduce any personal or sensitive information.

III Documentation and Data Quality

III.1 Metadata and documentation

Data organisation, metadata, and documentation:

The project follows a clear folder structure separating raw data (/data/raw/), processed data (/data/processed/), notebooks (/notebooks/), reports (/reports/), and source code (/src/). Raw data will remain unchanged, while all transformations and analyses will be stored as new processed files to ensure traceability. Versioning is handled through Git and GitHub. All changes to data processing scripts, notebooks, and documentation are tracked automatically via commits, providing a complete and transparent version history. File naming will follow a consistent structure that reflects content and processing steps. This setup ensures reproducibility, clear documentation of changes, and long-term maintainability of the research data.

The project will provide descriptive metadata to ensure that the datasets can be easily identified, understood, and reused. Metadata will include: dataset title, source URL, data origin, time period covered, variable descriptions (teams, goals, match results, home/away indicators), file formats, and licensing information. As there are no specific domain metadata standards required for this type of sports statistics data, metadata will be documented at the project level through a detailed README file. Each dataset will include clear naming conventions and accompanying descriptions in the /data/processed/ directory. Information about data provenance, reuse conditions, and processing steps will be provided in the documentation so that users can trace how the raw data were transformed. This ensures transparency, discoverability, and reusability of all research outputs. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

	<p>Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.</p> <p>As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.</p> <p>All analysis steps are documented in the Jupyter notebook (home_advantage_study.ipynb), including data loading, cleaning, transformations, and visualizations. The repository README describes the project structure, datasets, processing workflow, software used, and instructions for reproducing results. Processed data files and visual outputs are stored in /data/processed/ and /reports/figures/ to enable verification and reuse.</p>
<p>III.2 Data quality control</p>	<p>Data quality control:</p> <p>Data quality will be ensured through a combination of automated checks in the analysis scripts and manual inspection of the input data. After loading the raw CSV files, column types and value ranges are validated (e.g. dates, goals, league codes), and missing values or corrupted rows are flagged. Duplicate match records are removed based on league, season, date, and team identifiers. For each league and season, consistency checks verify that the number of home wins, away wins, and draws equals the total number of recorded matches and that goals scored and conceded balance across home and away teams.</p> <p>All cleaning and aggregation steps are implemented in a Jupyter notebook and version-controlled with Git, ensuring that any changes to the workflow are tracked and reproducible. A small random sample of matches is cross-checked manually against the original online sources to detect potential systematic errors in the download or parsing process.</p>
<p>IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation</p>	
<p>IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process</p>	<p>Storage and backup facilities:</p> <p>During the project, all data and code are stored in a structured project directory on the local workstation and in a private Git repository hosted on GitHub. The project directory (including /data/raw/, /data/processed/, /notebooks/, /src/ and /reports/) is additionally synchronised to TU Wien cloud storage (TUproCloud / home directory), which is backed up regularly by the university IT services. Raw data in /data/raw/ are treated as read-only and are never overwritten; all transformations produce new files in /data/processed/, which can always be regenerated from the version-controlled scripts and notebooks.</p> <p>Access to the GitHub repository and TU Wien storage is restricted to the project owner via authenticated accounts; no personal or sensitive data are processed, so standard institutional security measures are sufficient. This combination of local copies, Git version control, and TU Wien managed storage provides redundancy and protects against accidental deletion or hardware failure.</p> <p>Data security and protection of sensitive data:</p> <p>We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Access to data during research:</p>

	dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
	R1	writing	reading only	no access
	R2	writing	reading only	no access

IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation	Data publication and access conditions:															
	As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.															
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>dataset ID</th> <th>access conditions</th> <th>estimated publication date</th> <th>location for publication (repository)</th> <th>PID</th> <th>license</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>P1–P6 (processed match datasets: all_matches.csv, overall_distribution.csv, league_results_counts.csv, league_results_percent.csv, summary_all_matches.csv, summary_by_league.csv)</td> <td>open access, no embargo</td> <td>30 November 2025</td> <td>TU Wien Research Data repository – test instance (primary deposit); additional mirrors on Zenodo and GitHub</td> <td>Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17714127; DOI from TU Wien Research Data will be assigned upon deposit</td> <td>CC BY 4.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license	P1–P6 (processed match datasets: all_matches.csv, overall_distribution.csv, league_results_counts.csv, league_results_percent.csv, summary_all_matches.csv, summary_by_league.csv)	open access, no embargo	30 November 2025	TU Wien Research Data repository – test instance (primary deposit); additional mirrors on Zenodo and GitHub	Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17714127; DOI from TU Wien Research Data will be assigned upon deposit
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Methods or software needed to access and use data: The data are provided in standard tabular formats (.xlsx and .csv), which can be opened with common tools such as Excel, Python (pandas), or R. No specialized software is required. The folder structure and documentation in the repository support straightforward reuse.																

Long-term preservation and deletion of data:			
dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1–P6 (processed match datasets)	TU Wien Research Data repository – test instance (long-term preservation according to TU Wien policies); GitHub repository kept as an additional working copy, but not relied on as a preservation system	at least 10 years after publication	Re-use in teaching and student projects on research data management and sports analytics; replication and extension of the home-advantage study by students, lecturers, and sports data analysts interested in football match statistics-

The derived datasets P1–P6 as well as the analysis code and main Jupyter notebook will be published in the TU Wien Research Data repository (test instance) with open access under CC BY 4.0 (data) and MIT or similar license (code). The original input datasets R1 and R2 will not be re-published, but referenced with stable URLs and under their original licenses.

V Legal and Ethical Aspects

V.1 Legal aspects	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.</p>
	<p>Intellectual property rights and rights of use:</p> <p>All new research outputs created in this project (analysis code, Jupyter notebooks and derived datasets P1–P6) are owned by the project owner (Bartosz Ciesielski). The source code in the /src/ directory and the Jupyter notebooks in /notebooks/ will be released under the MIT license, allowing reuse, modification and redistribution, provided that copyright and license notices are preserved. All processed tabular datasets produced by the analysis (P1–P6, stored in /data/processed/) will be published under a CC BY 4.0 license, which permits reuse and redistribution for any purpose with appropriate attribution to the creator. The reused input datasets R1 and R2 remain under the terms and conditions and/or open-source licenses specified by their original providers; the project does not attempt to change or re-license these data, but only distributes derived, aggregated statistics that do not contain personal or sensitive information. License information for both the code and the derived datasets is documented in the repository README and corresponding LICENSE files, and will be mirrored in the TU Wien Research Data and Zenodo deposits to support transparent reuse.</p>

V.2 Ethical aspects**Ethical issues:**

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.